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Arboreal Flora of Durga Devi Hill Park of Pimpri Chinchwad

Cholke Pravin

Department of Botany, Waghire College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Saswad, MS, India

Deepa Bhalerao

Department of Botany, Nowrosjee Wadia College, Pune, MS, India

Bhor Abhishek

Department of Botany, Waghire College of Arts, Commerce and Science, Saswad, Pune

Abstracts

Pimpri-Chinchwad is part of Pune Metropolitan City of Maharashtra state, (India). It is a major industrial hub in Asia and an urban agglomeration of Pune. It includes the towns of Pimpri, Chinchwad, Nigdi, Akurdi, Ravet, Bhosari, Pimple-Gurav, Moshi, Punawale, and Sangavi, which are governed by a common municipal body, the Pimpri-Chinchwad Municipal Corporation (PCMC). It is towards the north-west of Pune city and is connected to the city centre via the Old Pune-Mumbai Highway. It is also recognized as Detroit of the East with the presence of many national and multinational automobile companies. Blessed with rich cultural heritage and history, Pimpri-Chinchwad is amongst the best developed cities in India. It is spread over a 177.3 sq. Km. area having more than 2,40,000 residential properties with a population over 17 lakhs. The municipal corporation provides facilities like road infrastructure, public transport, health services, water supply, sports facilities, gardens, solid waste management, drainage and sewage treatment plants, primary, secondary and higher education, and a garbage depot at Moshi.

Pimpri-Chinchwad has 164 gardens covering an area of about 405 acre, four lakes and an amusement park. There are also some private and government nurseries. Durga Devi hill park is a forest area developed by the PCMC near Nigdi. The arboreal flora of Durga Devi hill comprises cultivated tree species of which a very few number are wild trees. The present study documents the tree species planted on Durga Devi hill comprising 156 tree species from 46 distinct families Out of which 146 species are from Dicotyledonae and 10 species from Monocotyledonae. In this paper, the checklist of tree species along with the flower colour, period of flowering and vernacular names, if any, are provided.

Key words: Arboreal Flora, Pimpri-Chinchwad.

Introduction

Pimpri-Chinchwad is part of Pune Metropolitan City in the state of Maharashtra, India. Pimpri-Chinchwad lies in the Pavana, Mula and Indrayani basins. It is located between 18.37 and 18.61 degrees

north latitude and 73.48 to 73.80 degrees east longitude with elevation of 570 m above mean sea level. The total area of the city is 177.3sq.km. Pimpri-Chinchwad city is rich with various soil types including black soil, coarse grey soil and reddish soil. The soil is shallow and poor, and does not retain moisture. The Average Rainfall is 781.9 mms. The maximum temperature is 37 degrees Celsius and minimum temperature is 11 degrees Celsius. The arboreal flora of Pimpri-Chinchwad includes majority of cultivated species and very few number of wild tree species, which is very typical and interesting. Durga Devi Hill park is a forest developed by Pimpri-Chinchwad Municipal Corporation located at Nigdi. The Durga devi hill park is one of the aspects of Pimpri Chinchwad corporation and over 16000 trees have been planted over an area of 75 hectors. The arboreal flora of Durga Devi Hill park comprises of cultivated tree species and a very few number belongs from wild tree species. A very little attention has been paid to study the plant diversity of Pimpri-Chinchwad and corporation area. Cooke has published a, 'Flora of the Presidency of Bombay'; however he has covered very few plants from Pune district. The 'Flora of Maharashtra' is published by B. S. I. in 3 volumes (2000). The present study reveals that 156 tree species are planted on Durga Devi Hill park out of which 146 species are from Dicotyledonae while 10 species are from Monocotyledonae. In the present paper, the checklist of tree species along with the flower colour, period of flowering and vernacular names if any are provided.

Material and Method

The frequent visits were arranged from last two years to city corporation area in different seasons. All the collected specimens were numbered and properly processed. Specimens were identified by using various regional and national floras and available literature of Cooke T. (1901-1908), Ganorkar R. (2013), Hooker J.D. (1855), Naik, V.N (1998), Sharma B. D., S. Karhikeyan and N. P. Singh (1996), Singh N. P., and S. Karthikeyan. (2000), Singh, N. P., P. Lakshminarasimhan. S. Karthikeyan; and P. V. Prasanna. (2001), Yadav S. R., Sardesai M. M. (2002). Identification was confirmed by the plant experts of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune and Taxonomists of affiliated colleges of Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune. The voucher specimens were deposited in the Herbarium, Botany Department, Waghire college of Arts, commerce and Science, Saswad, Tal-Saswad, Pune. In the enumeration, the sequence of families has been followed as per Bentham and Hooker's classification. The nomenclature has been based on the latest taxonomic literature for each species; botanical name is followed by local name if any, colour of flowers and period of flowering.

Result and Discussion

The present study reveals the tree species planted on Durga Devi Hill; reports 156 tree species belongs from 46 Families were studied in Table 1. Out of which 146 species are from dicotyledonae, 10 species from monocotyledonae. Among 46 families, Fabaceae has the largest number of species followed by Moraceae.

Out of 156 plants, Genera like *Acacia*, *Cassia* and *Ficus* etc. are dominant. From The observations, it is concluded that Fabaceae is the dominant and leading Family, Followed by Moraceae, Rubiaceae, Apocynaceae, Bignoniaceae. Some of the rare trees in Pimpri-Chinchwad area observed during the survey.

The vegetation of Pune city and around is decreasing rapidly. A survey has revealed that there is decline in species richness but the arboreal flora belonging to various families has risen. The dominant families observed are Leguminosae, Malvaceae etc. (Nerlekar *et. al.*, 2016). It is very important to give emphasis on plantation of indigenous varieties during plantation programmes. The exotic species such as *Acacia*, *Cassia* are planted most commonly as they are fast growing trees but these trees are responsible for disturbance the biological chain depending upon the plants such as birds, animals and insects associated with these plants. b The emphasis should be given to the indigenous plants such as Tamarind, Neem, *Terminalia* in plantation programmes to maintain and restore the biological associations of plants and organisms depending upon them and therefore ecological systems.

Table 1

Sr. No	Botanical Name	Family	Monocot/ Dicot	Flowering Season	Flower Colour	Native
1.	<i>Acacia Arabica</i> (Lam.) Willd.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Aug. - Feb	yellow	Asia
2.	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> A. Cunn. ex. Bth.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Yellow	Australia
3.	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.f) Willd	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jul. - Feb.	Whitish yellow	South Asia
4.	<i>Acacia chundra</i> (L.f) Willd.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Pale yellow	India
5.	<i>Acacia ferruginea</i> DC.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - Mar	Pale yellow	Shrilanka
6.	<i>Acacia leucophloea</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Aug. - Feb	Whitish yellow	India
7.	<i>Acacia mangium</i> Willd.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - Mar	White	Australia
8.	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L) Willd.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Yellow	Africa, India
9.	<i>Adathoda vasica</i> Nees.	Acanthaceae	Eudicot	Nov.-Feb	Whitish-pink	Asia
10.	<i>Adenthera pavonina</i> L.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	March-Aug	Whitish-yellow	China, India
11.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.)Corr.	Rutaceae	Eudicot	April - Nov	Greenish-White	Asia
12.	<i>Agave sisalana</i> Perrine	Asparagaceae	Monocot	May-Aug	Greenish-Yellow	Mexico
13.	<i>Albizia lebbeck</i> (L.) Willd.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Apr. - Aug	White	Northern Australia
14.	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R.Br.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Dec. - Mar.	Greenish-White	India
15.	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) Willd.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Dec. - Mar.	Greenish-White	India

16.	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Anonaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Dec.	Green	America
17.	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. Ex De) Wall.	Combretaceae	Eudicot	Mar - Sept.	Greenish-Yellow	India
18.	<i>Aphanamixis polystachya</i> (Wall.) Parker	Meliaceae	Eudicot	Aug-Dec.	Greenish-Yellow	Asia
19.	<i>Aphanamixis polystachya</i> (Wall.)	Meliaceae	Eudicot	Aug-Dec.	Greenish-Yellow	Asia
20.	<i>Araucaria bidwillii</i> Hook.	Araucariaceae	Eudicot	April-Sep	yellowish	Australia
21.	<i>Areca catechu</i> L.	Arecaceae	Monocot	Throughout year	Yellow	Asia
22.	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Sept - Jan	Green	Southeast Asia
23.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> Juss.	Meliaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - June	white	Indian
24.	<i>Bambusa arundinacea</i> Willd.	Poaceae	Monocot	Once in life, Sept. - May.	Brown	Asia
25.	<i>Bambusa vulgaris</i> Sch.	Poaceae	Monocot	Jan-Oct.	Green,yellow	Asia
26.	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> L.	Leguminosae	Eudicot	Oct. - Jan.	Purple	Asia
27.	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	Leguminosae	Eudicot	Apr. - Oct	White, Yellow	Asia
28.	<i>Bauhinia roxburghiana</i> Voigt	Leguminosae	Eudicot	Sep-Jan	Whitish	India
29.	<i>Bixa orellana</i> L.	Bixaceae	Eudicot	Oct.-Dec	Reddish	America
30.	<i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i> Willd.	Nyctaginaceae	Eudicot	Jan-March	Pink	Asia
31.	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Malvaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - June	Red	Asia
32.	<i>Bridelia retusa</i> (L.) Spriang	Phyllanthaceae	Eudicot	May-Aug	Purplish White	Asia
33.	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lank.) Taub	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - June	Orange	India
34.	<i>Caesalpinia pulcherrima</i> (L.) Sw.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Yellow/Red	America
35.	<i>Calliandra haematocephala</i>	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Blood Red	America
36.	<i>Callistemon citrinus</i> Skeels	Myrtaceae	Eudicot	Sep-Dec	Red	Asia
37.	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R. Br.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Whitish Purple	Asia
38.	<i>Carrisa congesta</i> Wight.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	May- Oct.	White	White
39.	<i>Caryota urens</i> L.	Arecaceae	Monocot	Throughout year	Yellow	Asia
40.	<i>Cassia biflora</i> Miller.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jun-Dec	Yellow	India
41.	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Apr. - Oct.	Yellow	India
42.	<i>Cassia renigera</i> Wall.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jun- Sept	Pink	India
43.	<i>Cassia siamea</i> Lamk.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Aug. - June	Yellow	South Asia

44.	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i> Forst.	Casuarinaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - March	Green	Australia
45.	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i> (Thunb.) Tirveng	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Nov.	White	India
46.	<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i> Sw.	Rutaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	White	Asia
47.	<i>Clerodendrum inerme</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Lamiaceae	Eudicot	Nov- Jan	Greenish-Brown	India
48.	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	Arecaceae	Monocot	Throughout year	Green,White	Asia
49.	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> Forst.	Boraginaceae	Eudicot	Feb - June	White	Australia
50.	<i>Cordia gharaf</i> Eh. and Asch.	Boraginaceae	Eudicot	April - Oct	White	India
51.	<i>Cordia sebestena</i> L.	Boraginaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - July	Orange,Red	America
52.	<i>Courouputa guianensis</i> Abul.	Lecythidaceae	Eudicot	Sept. - Nov.	Red	America
53.	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> Linn.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - Oct.	White	India
54.	<i>Delonix regia</i> (Hook.) Raf.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	April - Sept.	Orange	Australia
55.	<i>Dendrocalamus strictus</i> (Roxb.) Nees	Moraceae	Eudicot	Nov- Feb.	yellowish Green	South Asia
56.	<i>Diospyros embryopteris</i> Pers.	Ebenaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - June	Yellow	South Asia
57.	<i>Diospyros nigrescens</i> (Datz.) Sald.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Jul-Oct	Greenish-White	South Africa
58.	<i>Dolichandron efalcata</i> (Wall ex. Dc.) Seem	Moraceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Dec.	White	India
59.	<i>Drypetes roxburghii</i> (Wall.) Hurusawa	Putranjivaceae	Eudicot	April - Oct	Green,White	South Asia
60.	<i>Duranta erecta</i> L.	Verbenaceae	Eudicot	Aug- Nov	Purple	Mexico
61.	<i>Dypsismadaga scariensis</i> Becc.	Arecaceae	Monocot	Throughout year	Yellow	Madagascar
62.	<i>Emblica officinalis</i> Gearth.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Feb - Oct	Green,White	India
63.	<i>Erythrina indica</i> Lam.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - June	Red	India
64.	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill.	Myrtaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - May	Whitish-Yellow	Australia
65.	<i>Ficus amplissima</i> Sm.	Moraceae	Eudicot	April - Sept.	Redish-Green	India
66.	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Moraceae	Eudicot	April - June	Redish-Green	India
67.	<i>Ficus benjamina</i> L.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Apr. - May	Redish-Green	India
68.	<i>Ficus carica</i> L.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Sept- Mar	Redish-Green	India
69.	<i>Ficus elastica</i> Roxb.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Jul-Oct	Whitish-Yellow	India

70.	<i>Ficus microcarpa</i> L. f. Nandruk WY	Moraceae	Eudicot	March - June	Whitish-Yellow	India
71.	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Feb. - June	Redish-Green	India
72.	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Moraceae	Eudicot	March - Aug.	Redish-Green	India
73.	<i>Ficus sp.</i>	Moraceae	Eudicot	Feb. - June	Redish-Green	India
74.	<i>Ficus variegata</i> Bl.	Moraceae	Eudicot	Jul- Oct	Green	Asia
75.	<i>Filicium</i> <i>decipiens</i> Thw.	Sapindaceae	Eudicot	Aug- Dec	White	Asia
76.	<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm. f.) Merr.	Salicaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - July	Greenish-White	India
77.	<i>Furcraea gigantea</i> Vent.	Agavaceae	Monocot	Aug- Dec	Greenish-White	South America
78.	<i>Gardenia</i> <i>jasminoides</i> Ellis.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	White	Asia
79.	<i>Gliricidia seipum</i> (Jacq)Kunth. ex. steu d.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - Mar	Pink	Central America
80.	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb.	lamiaaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - Jul	Yellow	India
81.	<i>Grevillea robusta</i> A. Cunn. ex R.Br.	Proteaceae	Monocot	Mar - July	Yellow	Australia
82.	<i>Hamelia patens</i> Jacq.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Aug-Oct	Red	America
83.	<i>Heterophragma</i> <i>quadriloculare</i> (Roxb.)Sch.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Aug-Oct	White	India
84.	<i>Hibiscus rosa-</i> <i>sinensis</i> L.	Malvaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Red, Yellow	Asia
85.	<i>Holoptelea</i> <i>integrifolia</i> (Roxb.)Planch	Ulmaceae	Eudicot	Sept- Nov	White	India
86.	<i>Ixora brachiata</i> Roxb.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Aug- Nov	Whitish purple	India
87.	<i>Ixora coccinea</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Red	India
88.	<i>Ixora parviflora</i> Vahl.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Aug- Nov	Whitish purple	India
89.	<i>Jacaranda acutifolia</i> Humb.&Bonpl.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Oct.	Purple	South America
90.	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Euphorbiaceae	Eudicot	Aug-Oct	Green	Mexico
91.	<i>Kigelia pinnata</i> (Lam.) Bth.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Oct.	Dark purple	Africa
92.	<i>Lagerstroemia</i> <i>parviflora</i> Roxb.	Lythraceae	Eudicot	Sept-Nov	Pink	India
93.	<i>Lagerstroemia</i> <i>reginae</i> Roxb.	Lythraceae	Eudicot	Aug - Oct.	Purple	Asia
94.	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Verbenaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Redish Yellow	South Africa
95.	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L.	Lythraceae	Eudicot	Jan. - Dec.	White	India
96.	<i>Leucaena</i> <i>latisiliqua</i> (L.)Gills.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	White	Asia

97.	<i>Mudhuca longifolia</i> J.F. Macbr.	Sapotaceae	Eudicot	Mar- May	Redish Brown	India
98.	<i>Mammeasuriga</i> (Buch.-Hamex Roxb.) Kosterm	Calophyllaceae	Eudicot	Apr-May	Redish White	India
99.	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Anacardiaceae	Eudicot	Jan - June	White	India
100.	<i>Manilkara zapota</i> (L.)Blumea	Sapotaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	White	India
101.	<i>Marsdenia volubilis</i> (L.f.) Cooke.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Jul-Sept	Green-White	China
102.	<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	Meliaceae	Eudicot	Jul. - Aug.	Violet	India
103.	<i>Michelia champaca</i> L.	Meliaceae	Eudicot	April - Sept	Bright-yellow	India
104.	<i>Millingtonia hortensis</i> L.F.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Sept. - Dec.	White	South Asia
105.	<i>Mimosa pselengi</i> L.	Sapotaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - Mar.	White	South Asia
106.	<i>Mitragynaparvifolia</i> (Roxb.) Korth.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Greenish-yellow	India
107.	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	Aug. - Mar.	White	Australia
108.	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Moringaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - April	White	Asia
109.	<i>Morus alba</i>	Moraceae	Eudicot	Jul. - Mar.	Whitish-Yellow	India
110.	<i>Muntingia calabura</i> L.	Muntingiaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	White	Southern Mexico
111.	<i>Murraya paniculata</i> (L.) Jack	Rutaceae	Eudicot	Feb-June	White	Southern China
112.	<i>Mussaenda glabrata</i> (Hook.f.) Hutch. ex Gamble	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	May-Nov	Yellow,pink	India
113.	<i>Nelomarckia cadamba</i> (Roxb.)Boss.	Rubiaceae	Eudicot	June-Aug	Yellow-Orange	Southeast Asia
114.	<i>Nerium oleander</i> Mill.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	March-June	Whitish-pink	India
115.	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i> Linn.	Oleaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	White	India
116.	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	purplish	India
117.	<i>Opuntia dillenii</i> Haw.	Cactaceae	Eudicot	May- Aug	Yellowish-Green	India
118.	<i>Peltophorum pterocarpum</i> (Dc.)Baker	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - June	Yellow	Southeast Asia
119.	<i>Petrea volubilis</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Eudicot	Aug- Nov	Violet-Purple	America
120.	<i>Phoenix syvestris</i> (L.)Roxb.	Arecaceae	Eudicot	Jan. - Oct.	White	Asia
121.	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.)Benth.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Jan.- June	Dull white	America
122.	<i>Plumeria alba</i> L.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Feb-may	Yellowish-White	India
123.	<i>Plumeria rubra</i> L.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Mar - Sept	White/Red	Mexico

124.	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i> (Sommer.) Thw	Annonaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Sept	Pale Green	India
125.	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Poerrie.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Feb - May	White purple	Asia
126.	<i>Prosopis spicigera</i> Linn.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Sept- Dec	Pinkish Yellow, White	Asia
127.	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Myrtaceae	Eudicot	Nov. - June	White	South America
128.	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> L.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Feb-june	Yellow	India
129.	<i>Pterospermum acerifolium</i> (L.) Willd.	Malvaceae	Eudicot	Dec. - June	White	South Asia
130.	<i>Pterygota alata</i> R.Br.(=Sterculia alata)	Malvaceae	Eudicot	Apr-May	Brownish-Yellow	India
131.	<i>Roystonea regia</i> Cook.	Arecaceae	Monocot	Sept. - Mar.	Greenish white	Mexico
132.	<i>Samanea saman</i> (Jacq.) Merr.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	May - Sept.	Pink	Mexico
133.	<i>Santalum album</i> L.	Santalaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Aug.	Brownish purple	South Asia
134.	<i>Sapindusema rignatus</i> Vahl.	Sapindaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - May	White/greenish white	India
135.	<i>Spathodea campanulate</i> Beauv	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Jul. - Mar	Orange Crimson	Africa
136.	<i>Stereospermum colais</i> Mabb.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Jun-Aug	Yellowish-White	India
137.	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) skeels	Myrtaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - June	White	South Asia
138.	<i>Tabebuia argentea</i> Britt.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - May	Bright yellow	South America
139.	<i>Tabebuia heptaphylla</i> (Vell.) Toledo	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - Aug	Pink	South America
140.	<i>Tabebuia rosea</i> Dc.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Dec - April	Pink	South Asia
141.	<i>Tabernaemontana coronaria</i> Br.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	White	India
142.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Fabaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - June	Yellow	India
143.	<i>Tecomastans</i> (L.) H.B.&K.	Bignoniaceae	Eudicot	Throughout year	Yellow	Mexico
144.	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.F.	Lamiaceae	Eudicot	Mar. - June	White	India
145.	<i>Terminalia alata</i> Heyeno.ex.Roth.	Combretaceae	Eudicot	Sept-Jan	Yellowish-Green	South Africa
146.	<i>Terminalia libellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Combretaceae	Eudicot	May - Sept.	Yellowish brown	South Africa
147.	<i>Terminalia catappa</i> L.	Combretaceae	Eudicot	Apr. - Oct.	Yellowish-Green	South Africa
148.	<i>Terminalia cuneata</i> Roth.	Combretaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - Nov.	Green	South Africa

149.	<i>Thespesia populnea</i> (L.) Soland	Malvaceae	Eudicot	Feb. - Sept.	Light-Yellow	South Africa
150.	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers.	Menispermaceae	Eudicot	Jun-Aug	Green	India
151.	<i>Trema orientalis</i> (L.) Bl.	Cannabaceae	Eudicot	Jun-Oct	Greenish white	South Asia
152.	<i>Vallisneria spiralis</i> (L.) Kuntze.	Apocynaceae	Eudicot	Jul. - Oct	White	India
153.	<i>Verbena pulchella</i> Sweet	Verbenaceae	Eudicot	May- Oct	Purple	South America
154.	<i>Woodfordia floribunda</i> Salisb.	Lythraceae	Eudicot	Jan- may	Red	India
155.	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i> Lam.	Rhamnaceae	Eudicot	Oct-Jan	Yellow	South Africa
156.	<i>Ziziphus xylopyra</i> Willd.	Rhamnaceae	Eudicot	Sept - Oct	Green	Africa

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